

HOW ABOUT US? AN ALLEGORY OF PERSON WITH DISABILITY LEARNERS IN THE CONDUCT OF LIMITED FACE-TO-FACE CLASSES

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How About Us? An Allegory of Person with Disability Learners in the Conduct of Limited Face-To-Face Classes

Clark Von Cagas-Rollon, * Cornelio R. Rollo
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This phenomenological study's purpose was to describe the experiences of PWD learners in the conduct of face-to-face classes after the COVID-19 pandemic in General Santos City for the school year 2022-2023. The study utilized a qualitative research design using a phenomenological approach, with 10 Junior and Senior High School learners with disability chosen through purposive sampling. Thematic content analysis was used as a data analysis tool. Considering the collected data, it revealed that the PWD learners were excited in the reopening of classes, self-determined and persevered, as well as experienced culture-shock during participation in limited face-to-face classes. Moreover, the themes for their coping strategies with various difficulties throughout their participation in limited face-to-face class were having a strong support system, having a positive mindset, and being adaptable to sudden change. Additionally, being a conqueror, being victorious amidst pandemic, and being a role model to others were the themes that resulted from the insights they shared for other learners with disabilities and to the academic community. Nevertheless, it was found out that all learners with disabilities were victorious amidst the pandemic. They conquered the challenges during the limited face-to-face classes and still were exhilarated to participate in the progressive in-person classes.

Keywords: *educational management, person with disability learners, limited face-to-face classes, pandemic, new normal education*

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has brought widespread disruption globally, affecting health, economies, and societal norms. Persons with disabilities face unique challenges during this time, disproportionately impacted due to factors such as pre-existing health conditions and the implementation of pandemic control measures like lockdowns and remote work. Research by Chen and McNamara (2020) and Sakellariou et al. (2020) supports this, highlighting the need for tailored policy responses to address their vulnerabilities. This situation calls for inclusive strategies such as accessible information, support services, and healthcare adaptations. Acknowledging this disparity urges collective action to advocate for inclusive policies and foster a supportive environment for individuals with disabilities.

In connection, globally, the COVID-19 pandemic has also profoundly altered the education system, especially for students with disabilities receiving special education services. The World Health Organization advised children with disabilities "to have fun, studying, reading, and interacting with others." It noted that people with disabilities may be disproportionately affected by the epidemic owing to disruptions to the services they rely upon. To ensure that special needs children continue learning and receiving public education and special services required by law, school districts should continue to provide educational services (World Health Organization [WHO], 2020).

Internationally, human rights legislation states that one of the most essential rights of a person is the right to education. Education acts as a multiplier, allowing people with or without disability to exercise human rights. As a result of education, economic, social, civil, political, and cultural rights are all enhanced. A good education, especially for students with disabilities, boosts one's self-esteem and allows for more effortless social mobility. As a result, it is necessary for every human being, with disabilities or not, to practice their right to education (De Beco, 2022).

Regarding COVID-19 infections as of March 20, 2022, the Philippines ranked second among Southeast Asian nations with 3,672,661 million cases. Due to this, everyone can be susceptible and heightened by burnout during the worldwide COVID-19 pandemic. Persons with disabilities, on the other hand, have the most unheard and vulnerable voices. As a result, PWDs were at a disadvantage due to social exclusions and biases. Employment, social roles, and educational access have all been issues in the past until today. These challenges eventually led to feelings of inadequacy and self-doubt, which was reasonable evidence that people with disabilities are subjected to opposing views from non-disabled people. Stereotypes and alienation of people with disabilities were viewed as a source of shame, humiliation, and inequity in society. PWDs have the same rights as other citizens. The right to vote, live independently in the community, receive social assistance, access justice, and receive an education, especially during this pandemic (Chen & McNamara, 2020; Sakellariou et al., 2020).

The seven categories of impairments were listed in the Philippines' Magna Carta for Disabled Persons, Republic Act 7277: psychosocial disability, chronic illness-related disability, learning disability, mental disability, visual disability, orthopedic disability, and communication disability. The disabilities above encountered similar prejudice and exclusion from the workplace, community, and educational institutions. To add more, Department of Education Order No. 72, s. 2009, as cited in the study of Alam Ashraf, made a strong case for the necessity for special needs children to get an adequate education in a standard or inclusive setting. Accepting all

students with the help of the community, parents, and school personnel, regardless of their race, size, shape, color, aptitude, or handicap, is the principle of inclusive education (Alam, 2022; Fontanilla-Pimentel, 2020).

On the contrary, a child's disability can be one of the most marginalizing aspects of his or her life. In education during this COVID-19 pandemic, formulating plans to meet the educational requirements of students with disabilities in the classroom, districts, regions, and countries with very restricted resources can be difficult even while problems with implementing inclusive education systems exist. Inclusive education—which fully involves all students, including children with disabilities or other learning challenges has been shown to be highly effective in helping all students learn during the pandemic (Hayes & Bulat, 2017).

In early 2022, former President Rodrigo Roa Duterte approved the Department of Education's proposal to expand in-person classes, subject to the safety measures set by the Health department and the concurrence of local governments and parents. Students, both without and with disability, were preparing to participate. Hence, the expansion of in-person classes was progressive in areas under Alert Levels 1 and 2. In cooperation with the Interior and Justice departments, the DepEd and the Department of Health determined the scope and procedures for extending limited face-to-face classes and other school-based initiatives.

Furthermore, knowledge of how the pandemic has impacted the education and support services provided to students with disabilities has been essential in shaping policy and practice as a concerned citizen and public school teacher. Although there needs to be more statistics, an increasing number of complaints about due process and investigations by the Philippine Department of Education verify anecdotal evidence that students like them have yet to receive the necessary assistance and resources to learn regularly.

As a researcher, in order to fully comprehend service disruptions and the pandemic's effects on students with disabilities, I realized the need for an urgent research agenda. We cannot successfully develop and put into practice solutions to alleviate weaknesses and speed up learning without the finer details. The researcher also sought the experiences of students with disabilities participating in the conduct of in-person classes. As a result, this project would increase sensitivity to PWD students' experiences in the conduct of face-to-face or in-person classes. The findings of this study would add to their knowledge and could be used as a reference for school evaluations and future research.

Research Questions

This study's primary goal was to explore and describe the experiences of PWD students in limited face-to-face classes and investigated the challenges encountered in the learning environment and ways of coping with the challenges. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. How are PWD learners' challenges described in the conduct of limited face-to-face education:
 - 1.1. How do students with disabilities experience face-to-face classes in the new normal?
 - 1.2. How do PWD students cope and deal with the challenges during face-to-face classes in the new normal?
 - 1.3. What are the insights of the PWD students towards the progressive expansion of face-to-face classes that they can share to other students and to the academic community?

Methodology

Research Design

This study sought to investigate the sentiments and ideas of PWD learners about their experiences during limited face-to-face education. The study used a phenomenological methodological approach to pursue this qualitative study to understand PWD learners' interpretive experience of their reflective processes as they participated limited face-to-face classes. Reflection is an interior process that takes place over time and in the context of human life experiences. As described, qualitative research provides meaning to the participants' experiences. The qualitative method was considered appropriate for comprehending the meaning, interpretation, and construction of participants' subjective experiences. It depends on the practice as well as the problem structure. More research is needed in special education to better understand learners' perceived ability and willingness to be part of the limited face-to-face class. Taking a holistic approach to this study and the integrated report, a more complete understanding of the situation (Merriam & Tisdell, 2015; Percy et al., 2015; Williams, 2021).

Moreover, the methodologies were elaborated upon, as well as the data analysis and the assessments of trustworthiness, constraints, and ethical assurances. In the face of a crisis, school is one of the key venues where teachers and their students continue their social and emotional development. As stated by Erikson's adult stage of human development theory, administrators should be aware that the COVID-19 global pandemic threatens teachers' social-emotional development. The World Health Organization (WHO) Kawatsu and Ohkado 2017 published a guideline to assist schools on December 11, 2020. Considering this study and the participants gave them a better grasp of the situation. PWD learners may have had time to reflect on previous experiences that they might incorporate into their new journey now that schools have restarted. Participants were interviewed in semi-structured interviews, which were subsequently transcribed by the researcher (Bull et al., 2020; Dempsey et al., 2016).

Participants

This study involved ten PWD learners from various schools in General Santos City who participated in face-to-face classes. They underwent in-depth interviews and focus group discussions, adhering to proper health protocols. The researchers chose ten cases of PWD students, following Gill and Baillie's (2018) recommendation to choose 3-25 people who have encountered the same phenomenon. Elliot's (2020) guiding principles for selecting participants for phenomenological studies include the importance of the individual case to the group study, the diversity of the individual cases compared to other participants, and the potential benefits of the individual case when examined alongside the other cases. This study aimed to meet Stake's 2013 guiding principles of relevance and diversity by involving high school PWD learners aged 12-18. The participants were legally entitled to a disability and were within the scope of Republic Act 7277 of the Philippines, known as the Magna Carta for Disabled Persons. The study also met Stake's third guiding principle, the opportunity to learn from the cases. The researcher did not impose gender limitations or exclude PWD learners based on socioeconomic status, education, or family background. The data analysis process involved participant's words and transcriptions, and the connecting procedure was used to analyze the participants' experiences in face-to-face classes.

Procedure

In the conduct of the study, first, the researcher sent a research proposal to the Office of the Graduate Studies for ethical review; once the office sent their approval, he requested an endorsement letter from the RMMC-General Santos Graduate School through the office of the Dean to conduct the study; then, he sent a letter to the validators for them to validate the interview guide questions; letter of invitation with the informed consent form approved by the RMMC-Graduate School was sent to the informants, the researcher made sure that the necessary ethical considerations was followed.

Second, the researcher explained to the respondents the study's primary purpose and that their participation was voluntary. The participants were encouraged to be open when answering the form, and I also gave instructions on how to fill it out. The researcher emphasized a manner of recruitment free of coercion, undue influence, or inducement; after the consent form was distributed, the researcher collected it personally to secure confidentiality.

Third, the researcher also conducted the interview. He asked the participants the research questions through one-on-one, in-depth interviews; PWD learners in face-to-face classes were allowed to express their ideas freely. During the interview, the researcher recorded everything from day 1 of the interview up to the last day. Also, the researcher made sure to take note of everything they shared, including their body movement as they unfolded their experiences. The interviews were conducted in a quiet and comfortable setting to ensure the participants felt at ease. The researcher also employed active listening techniques to encourage detailed and honest responses.

Fourth, the data results were transcribed, analyzed, and interpreted confidentially; the researcher also ensured that the data were saturated.

Finally, the findings were summarized to arrive at the implications, recommendations for future researchers, and concluding remarks. The researcher plans to publish the results and findings in an online journal for further dissemination.

Data Analysis

According to Cooksey et al. 2019, data analysis in qualitative research refers to the methodical search and organization of interview transcripts, observation notes, and other non-textual materials that the researcher collects to improve comprehension of the event. The researcher took the following actions to do this: First, the researcher familiarized the data by reading it multiple times and searching for fundamental findings or trends. Part of this process involved data transcription. He then went over the research objectives again and came up with some questions that she might use the data to address. This led the researcher to create a system called coding or indexing, where he has already coded several general concepts, thoughts, behaviors, or phrases (Diomampo & Quines, 2023).

In addition, the researcher identified trends and linkages, developed themes by identifying the most frequently asked topics, and identified opportunities for additional study. The researcher utilized narrative analysis to examine content from diverse sources, such as discourses and perceptions. The main focus was on utilizing the experiences and narratives provided by participants to address the study inquiries. In the interim, the information was analyzed thematically (Venkatesan, 2020).

According to Zahavi (2021), phenomenological reduction in data analysis is made of both epoché and reduction proper. In epoché, we abandon acknowledging the world that holds us captive. In contrast, reduction tells the "moment" in which we come to the elevating awareness that the world's acceptance is not absolute.

Results and Discussion

This section presented the findings of the study based on the gathered data taken from the participants.

This study included 10 participants currently studying in High School, particularly in the General Santos City Division. Four (4) male and six (6) female PWD learners were enrolled in this school year. They were selected based on their condition and disability and the recommendation of their SPED Coordinator. The in-depth interview was conducted with two males and three females. To begin with,

the researcher's first informant is Professor Xavier. He is a 17-year-old Orthopedically Handicapped learner from Fatima National High School, currently in Grade 12. On the other hand, Jean Grey is a 17-year-old learner currently attending Fatima National High School; she has a Speech Impairment. Further, another learner from a big school has happily accepted the chance to be part of this research. He is Eye Boy, a 13-year-old PWD learner who has been schooling at Ireneo L. Santiago National High School and is now in grade seven.

Another General Santos City National High School learner, Storm, participated in the interview. She is 16 years old, a Grade 12 student with Clubbed Foot. Another participant from Lagao National High School contributed to the data collection—a 12-year-old learner with Visual Impairment, the pseudonym of Scott Summers. One focus group discussion was held with five participants (three females and two male learners). They were all chosen in the same manner as the participants and came from different schools. Participants in the focus groups were students with disabilities from different schools in General Santos City. Mystique is a 14-year-old learner with visual impairment. She has been studying at Labangal National High School and is in Grade Eight. On the other hand, Wolverine is a 13-year-old learner who conquered challenges despite having a Speech Impairment. He is currently in his eighth grade at Labangal National High School. Similarly, Magneto is 15 years old and has been studying at Labangal National High School. He has Visual Impairment. In addition, Rouge is a 12-year-old student who is Orthopedically Handicapped and is currently studying at Labangal National High School. Further, Angel is the last FGD participant in this study. She is 16 years old and has a Visual Impairment. She is currently studying at Labangal National High School.

The discussion was held to gain additional information, insight, and constructs on the PWD learners' limited face-to-face education journey and strengthen and confirm the findings. In concealing the participants' true identities, their real names were avoided during the discussion, and they were also assigned screen names. This approach ensured confidentiality and encouraged open, honest sharing of experiences. The insights gathered will contribute significantly to understanding the challenges and needs of PWD learners in educational settings.

Both research groups responded to the same set of questions. The first respondents from the FGD were the researcher's students at General Santos City National High School. They were the researcher's students, so he discovered their experiences and challenges in the limited face-to-face education journey. The researcher arranged meetings with the recommended participants with the assistance of their school principals and colleagues. Their assistance in gathering data and information was greatly appreciated. Additionally, the collaboration of these key stakeholders ensured a comprehensive understanding of the educational landscape.

Furthermore, the researcher's colleagues assisted him greatly in making the information more understandable. This collaboration builds trust, essential in retrieving their personal information and sincerely sharing their limited face-to-face education experiences and journeys. Some informants in the in-depth interview were the researcher's students with disabilities. However, some of the participants in the Focus Group Discussion (FGD) were referred to me by the SPED Coordinators of the different schools. Though some were initially concerned, they quickly relaxed after the researcher assured them of the study's confidentiality. They were very cooperative in answering all their interview questions. Because of their experiences in limited face-to-face education, one could still feel their happiness and apprehension through their voices and facial gestures.

Moreover, the focus group discussion was fascinating, and the interaction was unexpected. The researchers could hear how they reacted to the other participants' personal experiences in their low voices. Some had similar experiences, but each had an impressive story about their difficulties and lessons learned on that quest. The researcher ensured that they signed the consent certificate and that all equipment, such as audiotapes, the researcher's phone recorder, and pen audio recorders, were used with the assurance that everything that occurred during the interview and group discussions would be kept confidential. In strengthening the trust and confidence of the participants, the recorded tapes were played for them to listen to, and if there were any portions they wish to be deleted, this could be done. Even the recorded notes would be shown to them for their review and approval.

The researcher gathered and examined all the data, classifying it for better understanding. Summarizing the vast amount of data and communicating key findings were critical components of data analysis in research studies. The approach included data reduction, data visualization, conclusion drawing, and verification. Data reduction involves abstracting unimportant data and translating it into a material that is easily understandable. Thematic analysis, a sorting and categorization technique, was used to pair and organize material. The researcher employed professional data analyst skills to manage the data, sorting and categorizing large amounts of qualitative data and retrieving words and phrases. The data was consolidated and manageable after sorting and classification. Participants' information was sorted and clustered into emergent themes in experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights (Saldana, 2018; Thomas et al. (2022).

On the other hand, data display was the arrangement of information using graphic organizers, such as tables, graphs, charts, and matrices, to help the viewer make inferences. It goes beyond data reduction by displaying the data in an organized and systematic manner, making the viewer aware of the relationships between various pieces of information. Higher-order categories may emerge at this point. The final stages of qualitative analysis involve drawing conclusions and confirming them, revisiting the data to assess their implications and verifying the emerging findings (Akinyode & Khan, 2018; Mezmir, 2020).

The researcher's findings should support those of other investigators, and alternative interpretations should be considered before developing a coherent argument for validity assessment. When interpreting the report, the researcher must consider which data to

include and discard, and the interpretation should be expressed in a clear, precise manner. A well-written, engaging, and accessible report provides sufficient description to allow the reader to grasp the basis for an interpretation and understand the description (Alase, 2017; Gloede et al. 2021; Johnson et al., 2020).

In other words, the phenomenological researcher has conducted in-depth interviews and focus groups with participants who have experienced the journey of Person with Disabilities (PWD) learners. They have searched through each participant's statements for relevant and meaningful aspects of their experiences about the phenomenon of interest. These statements were organized into emergent themes, which were the aspects of the participants' experiences that they had shared. The researcher then extracted relevant statements and integrated them into emergent themes to understand the challenges PWD learners face in conducting limited face-to-face classes. The aim was to understand the essential structure of the phenomenon and the fundamental features of the experiences described by the majority of the participants.

Experiences of Students with Disabilities towards the Face-to-face Classes in the New Normal

The data collected on the experiences of the study participants revealed emergent themes, as presented in Table 1. These themes are Excitement in the Re-opening of Classes, Self-determination and Perseverance, and Culture Shock.

Table 1. *Experiences of Students with Disabilities towards the Face-to-face Classes in the New Normal*

Cluster Themes	Emergent Themes
Feeling of happiness Sense of excitement Desire to attend face-to-face classes Inclination to attend face-to-face classes Eagerness to participate in class Strong excitement in face-to-face classes	Excitement in the Reopening of Classes
trying to do my best... Strive to do one's best Help each other Pushing oneself Striving hard Strong desire to continue to study	Self-determination and perseverance
Feeling of shock Feeling of unfamiliarity Scared of the unknown Feeling of surprise Shocked... Challenging situation	Culture-shocked

Excitement in the Reopening of Classes

Almost all the key informants and participants of the IDI disclosed a high level of excitement at the re-opening of the classes; they were pleased that face-to-face classes had begun, and they had the chance again to see their teachers and meet new friends. They also shared that they prefer face-to-face classes to distance learning because seeing their teachers and mentors is more fun. According to studies, the quality of instruction is mainly determined by the teachers inside the classroom. Specifically, a teacher's enthusiasm for their work leads students to believe that school instruction is of more excellent quality (Lazarides et al., 2021).

Self-determination and perseverance

PWD students had opinions regarding their tenacity and resilience in participating in the limited face-to-face classes. Their desire to provide a better future for their family was part of their motivation. For some, the only motivation was to give it their all and prove to others that they could still succeed despite their circumstances. Additionally, a few felt driven to serve as role models for others. However, the researcher saw one thing in common with most of them: their incredible perseverance and self-determination.

Culture-shocked

Disoriented feelings are described as culture shock, uncertainty, and discomfort that individuals may experience when encountering unfamiliar cultural norms, values, and practices. It is a common psychological phenomenon when people are exposed to a new cultural environment, whether through travel, relocation, or immersion in a different social setting (Deborah & Barry, 2022). Our PWD learners also experienced this psychological phenomenon at the beginning of the limited face-to-face classes. Most of them needed help to adjust to the number of activities that were being given to them by the teachers as well as the environment of the school.

PWD Students' Coping Mechanisms in Dealing with the Challenges during the Face-To-Face Classes in the New Normal

Positive Mindset

A positive mindset is a mental attitude focused on optimism, hope, and constructive thinking, even in challenging or adverse situations. It involves cultivating a belief in one's ability to overcome obstacles, learn from failures, and see opportunities for growth and improvement (Achor, 2018). The power of positivity in shaping personal and professional success, arguing that happiness and positivity

are not outcomes of success but rather precursors to it. He suggests that individuals can enhance their performance, relationships, and overall well-being by adopting a positive mindset.

Table 2. *PWD students' coping mechanism in dealing with the challenges during the face-to-face classes in the new normal*

Cluster Themes	Emergent Themes
Happiness as an emotional refuge Expressing gratitude and offering warm smile Maintaining an optimistic outlook Keeping a hopeful attitude Maintaining positive mindset Embracing positivity An optimist Positive thinker	Positive mindset
Receiving substantial assistance by family Feeling of affirmation Receiving positive reinforcement Encouraged Sense of reassurance Family is the driving force Being motivated	Strong support system
Following protocols Adhering to procedures Complying to guidelines Being vigilant Being observant	Strong capacity for adaptation

Strong support system

Most PWD students in the IDI and FGD felt supported by their relatives, classmates, and instructors despite their difficulties in the limited face-to-face classes. According to Devaney et al. (2023), the support system is a network of people, teams, or institutions that offer someone in need or, during a crisis, emotional, practical, or informational help is referred to as a support system. Family, friends, classmates, mentors, therapists, support groups, and local resources can all be a part of this network. Support networks are essential for building mental health, resilience, and coping strategies in difficult life situations.

Strong capacity for adaptation

Regarding the coping strategies of PWD students who took part in the limited face-to-face classes, one of their strategies is having a strong capacity for adaptation to their environment. Six IDI and FGD informants shared their sentiments.

The Insights of the PWD Students Towards the Progressive Expansion of Face-To-Face Classes that they can share to other Students and to the Academic Community

Table 3. *The Insights of the PWD Students Towards the Progressive Expansion of Face-To-Face Classes that they can share to other Students and to the Academic Community*

Cluster Themes	Emergent Themes
Strong desire to go to school Having driven to success Having a string ambition for achievement Strong desire to thrive in life Validation of one's abilities Desire to reciprocate parents' effort Desire for educational completion	Conqueror
Attaining success Accomplished one's aspiration Triumphant in the face of COVID-19 Liberated to do one's goals and aspirations	Victorious amidst pandemic
A dream weaver Maintaining resilience during pandemic Exemplary figure amidst the pandemic A go-getter Sense of diligence A great aspirant Sense of appreciation to authorities	Great role model

Conqueror

Their encouragement from friends and family enabled them to overcome this adversity. Five IDI informants shared the following coping strategies. Other PWD learners who encounter circumstances similar to those of the informants would find great inspiration in the ideas they have provided like having the strong desire to go to school every day and being goal driven at all times.

Victorious amidst pandemic

As they recount their experiences participating in limited face-to-face classes and their success stories. Informants imparted their wisdom on how to prevail in a pandemic. Such as the eagerness to attain success, having the feeling of accomplishments, feeling triumphant in the face of COVID-19, and having the feeling of liberation to do one's goal and aspirations.

Great role model

Due to their experiences and challenges during limited face-to-face classes, our informants want to be role models to other physically, mentally, emotionally, and spiritually challenged students. They want to show them that if they conquered and came out victorious above all these challenges, well then, so can they.

The findings highlighted various experiences faced by the participants as they participated in the conduct of limited face-to-face classes. This study revealed that PWD learners were excited about reopening the classes. They were eager to participate in face-to-face classes after two years of homeschooling, to meet new friends, and to see their teachers. This feeling manifested that learners with disabilities were determined to participate in face-to-face classes.

Moreover, Professor Xavier (pseudonym), an orthopedically handicapped learner who shared his experience about his CSS class on the second floor of the building, said that facing that challenge did not let him lose his eagerness to learn and did not lessen his excitement about going to school. However, Storm (pseudonym) shared the same experience. She was pleased that face-to-face classes finally returned because she could learn new things with her friends and classmates. She shared that learning at home was difficult because she was still determining if her comprehension was correct. Her parents also did not know and could not teach her because they did not finish their schooling.

Additionally, based on their response, learners were generally excited about reopening face-to-face classes. Being excited is also part of intrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation is derived from the expectation that an activity will be pleasurable (Kadous & Zhou, 2018). Intrinsic motivation contrasts with extrinsic motivation in that the anticipated pleasures are inherent in performing an activity rather than from external factors (Kirkman et al., 2004). Individuals driven by intrinsic motivation will engage in an activity willfully and without coercion of external forces.

As the researcher interviewed the informants, he could see through their faces and feel their determination and perseverance in finishing their schooling through their responses. To achieve that goal, they always responded that they should participate in face-to-face classes, which is vital to achieving their dreams. They were not selfish because they always included their family in their aspirations in life. Giving them a comfortable life when they finish schooling is the ultimate success that they seek. That is why they always have hope and strive to achieve their goals.

Having the drive to achieve success is very important for a learner. According to Wehmeyer and Shogren (2016), self-determination is crucial since it affects psychological health and well-being. Another new emerging best practice is encouraging self-determination when working with specific populations, including people with intellectual disabilities.

After two years of the pandemic, learners with and without disabilities experienced culture shock after participating in face-to-face classes. On our first day of class in grade seven, some students cried because their parents had left them at school. They were not accustomed to the feeling of being independent, and they were overwhelmed by the diversity of people they encountered.

Taking into account the experience of Eye Boy, wherein he was not accustomed to interacting with other people. He said that he did not want to mingle with other students because he felt like other students were judging him because of his disability. He has selected friends, and he trusted them with all his heart. Furthermore, "Culture shock" is a normal process of adapting to a new culture (Aryani et al., 2021). It is a period when an individual realizes how their new culture and their native culture differ and clash in terms of values and conventions. Common emotions include wrath, homesickness, anxiety, and perplexity.

The participants of this study learned to cope with the challenges that came with their lived experience. They developed a positive mindset in participating in the limited face-to-face classes and a strong support system given by their family and friends in school. They also developed adaptability during their journey as PWD learners.

Three essential themes emerged from the analysis of data gathered through in-depth interviews and a focus group discussion: a positive mindset, a strong support system, and adaptability. Once again, the researcher observed that the participants' coping mechanisms followed a logical pattern. According to Friedman (2023), positive thinking does not mean ignoring life's less pleasant situations. In simple terms, positive thinking entails viewing unfavorable situations in a more constructive and upbeat light. A person anticipates the best rather than the worst. He thinks the best is going to happen, not the worst.

Having a positive mindset is essential for learners with disabilities because it helps them be motivated even though many challenges come along the way. Many of the learners that the researcher interviewed are positive thinkers. They always see the bright side of many things, just like one informant, Professor Xavier (pseudonym). He shared that positive thinking relieves him of depression and helps a person avoid depression.

According to Pretty et al. (2005), a robust support network offers mental and emotional advantages, ranging from elevated self-worth to reduced blood pressure. Support systems also assist students in reducing mental anguish and improving their capacity to handle pressure. A person's social network and support system impact his general health; those with close friends typically live longer and have more robust immune systems.

In the case of Storm (pseudonym), she said that her family supports her and motivates her to participate in face-to-face classes. They inspire her to do well in school and perform her best in whatever she does. Furthermore, her friends chat and message her with words of encouragement to pursue her studies and never give up, though there may be problems and hardships that she may encounter along the way. A strong support system motivates an individual to cope with different problems in life. To add more, Nelson et al. (2007) define adaptation as the intentional process of altering in response to stress and expectation of external stimuli. Significant changes had happened to our school system after the two years of pandemic had struck the nation. After classes reopened, many protocols were implemented to lessen the risk of students with or without disability contracting the virus. Due to these circumstances, the researcher's informants shared how they coped with changes in their environment while participating in face-to-face classes. Most of them said that wearing masks, using alcohol, and avoiding crowds as their strategies to avoid acquiring the virus, given that they have a disability. For them, knowing how to adapt to change was the most crucial weapon so that they could continue to pursue their dream: a proper education.

After examining their lived experiences and developing coping mechanisms in light of the phenomenon under study, the participants had insights to share with other students like them and the academe. Three essential themes emerged after data analysis: being a conqueror, victorious amidst a pandemic, and a great role model. All in all, the researcher's informants are undoubtedly conquerors of many challenges. Face-to-face classes have sparked their wilting hearts' desire to achieve their goals in life. Many hoped to have a business that would help their family in the future, just like the dream of Jean Grey (pseudonym). She dreams of building her bakeshop so that her father will no longer have to work in other bakeshops. She wants to give her father his business to manage so that he does not have to go the extra mile when he gets old.

Hearing this sentiment from Jean Grey (pseudonym) brought joy and gratitude to my heart. With her power to conquer different challenges in life and with the guidance of the school community and her parents, I know she can achieve that.

Merriam-Webster stated that victory is overcoming a rival or adversary in combat. In this case, that battle is the COVID-19 pandemic, and the opponent is the Coronavirus. During the pandemic, PWD learners fought hard to continue their education even in modular times. Now that face-to-face classes had reopened, they felt victorious because they had surpassed that stage of their lives.

In the case of Eye Boy, he said that he felt victorious because he endured the pandemic and still did all the things he liked, although COVID-19 is still around. He sees in the future that no student with or without disability would wear a mask anymore because he prayed that COVID-19 would be neutralized or better yet eradicated.

According to Allen and Collison (2020), role models are frequently recommended as a means of inspiring people to establish and meet lofty objectives, particularly for those who belong to marginalized groups in achievement settings. Being a role model to other learners with disabilities is one of the things the informants want to share with other students who are like them. The informants want others to see that if they could come out victorious against all the challenges that the pandemic had brought them, they could also conquer all the challenges that would come along their path. They always say that learners should not let the virus take over their lives. Learn to adapt, learn to live with it, and learn how to avoid it. Obey the protocols that the province or the national government has given and be respectful to other people. Do not just be a good follower but also be a good role model to other people because it is given that great role models are great followers.

Conclusions

This phenomenological qualitative study would aid school administrators, teachers, parents, and students in better understanding the viewpoints and experiences of PWD students in the conduct of limited face-to-face classes. As far-reaching implications of this phenomenological qualitative study extend into the very fabric of educational landscapes, advocating for a comprehensive transformation in how PWD learners experience the limited face-to-face classes after the COVID-19 pandemic.

Generally, PWD learners were excited to participate in face-to-face classes. They are determined to continue their education, so they persevere to go to school every day, given that they have experienced many challenges.

One of the challenges they experienced was culture shock, where they were overwhelmed by the sudden change of the school environment from home. PWD learners cope with different problems by having a positive mindset. They also have a strong support system provided by their families and friends and are adaptable to the change in the new normal.

In conclusion, PWD learners who participated in the progressive face-to-face classes were naturally born conquerors. They overcame the struggle of being a PWD learner who experienced the pandemic and now are participating in progressive face-to-face classes. They came out victorious amidst the COVID-19 pandemic because they were well-supported and guided by their parents. Due to conquering these challenges, they were inspired to be a great role model to other learners with special needs. Ultimately, they want other PWD learners to see that if they can conquer these obstacles they have experienced during the new normal, other may also conquer all the hindrances that obstruct their path to success.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Clark Von Cagas Rollon

Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges – Philippines

Cornelio R. Rollo, PhD, LPT

Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges – Philippines